

Quantum Versus Classical Periodicity in Bound States

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There exists recent literature concerning quantum revival structure and quantum periodicity approaching classical periodicity in the high energy limit (1) and references within). In (1), quantum revival is applied to $\langle x \rangle$ to calculate a quantum period which equals the classical period for an infinite well potential. The calculation is based largely on the form $\exp(-iEt)$ and so also holds in special relativity for the infinite well. One main result of (1) is to show that $\text{Period} = 2\pi\hbar / (E_n - E_m)$. (Note: If E_n and E_m are very close and $n=m+1$, then $E_n - E_m = dE/dn$ at E_n).

Here, we try to obtain the same result follows by focusing on a classical conservation of energy result with dp being restricted to the free particle result $2\pi\hbar/L$ for the infinite well potential. We then consider the case of a potential $V(x)$ and argue that in the high energy limit, even a quantum particle is essentially limited to the distance between the classical turning points. Thus, the set of $\exp(ipx)$ s used must satisfy infinite well potential boundary conditions and dp again equals $\hbar 2\pi/L$. We use the difference of classical energy conservation equations to show that: $(E_n - E_m) dt = dx dp$ with dp being the constant $\hbar 2\pi/L$ and obtain an identical equation for high energy level quantum period as in the infinite well case.

Quantum Revival and the Classical Period

In (1), it is argued that when considering a quantum wavefunction:

$$W(x,t) = \sum_j \exp(-i E_j t) W_j(x) \quad ((1))$$

one may find a revival time such that $W(x,t) = W(x, t + T_{\text{revival}})$. (1), however, argues {using the infinite well potential as an example} that the key quantity on which to focus is:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle x \rangle &= \left\{ \sum_n \exp(i E_n t) \langle n | \right\} \times \left\{ \sum_m \exp(-i E_m t) | m \rangle \right\} \\ &= \sum_{m,n} \langle n | x | m \rangle \exp(-i(E_m - E_n) t) \quad ((2)) \end{aligned}$$

One sees various periods, $2\pi\hbar / (E_m - E_n)$, with the smallest $E_m - E_n$ yielding the largest period which governs the overall system. If one considers the high n limit and picks n as some large number, then $n=m+1$ yields the smallest $E_m - E_n$. Thus:

$$\text{Overall period for } \langle x \rangle = 2\pi\hbar / (E_n - E_{n+1}) \approx 2\pi\hbar / dE/dn \text{ at } n \quad ((3))$$

This result applies to the square well potential, but should hold in general and for special relativity as well.

For the square well potential,

$T_{\text{classical}} = L/v = Lm/p$ where $p = \hbar \cdot 2\pi n/L$ so $T_{\text{classical infinite well}} = Lm / \{ \hbar \cdot 2\pi n \}$ ((4))

T_{quantum} from ((3)) = $m / (2\pi \hbar n)$ where $E_n = 1/(2m) \{ \hbar \cdot 2\pi n/L \}^2$

Thus: $T_{\text{classical}} = T_{\text{Quantum}}$ ((4)) for a square well potential when one uses the periodicity for an infinite well potential.

One may also apply this result to a harmonic oscillator. Classically, regardless of amplitude (i.e. energy), the period is:

$T_{\text{classical oscillator}} = 2\pi \sqrt{m/k}$ ((5))

$T_{\text{quantum oscillator}} = 2\pi \hbar / (d/dn \hbar \sqrt{k/m} (n+5)) = \sqrt{m/k} \cdot 2\pi$ ((6))

$T_{\text{classical oscillator}} = T_{\text{quantum oscillator}}$ using the periodicity of $\langle x \rangle$ ((7))

Alternative Approach Which Does Not Use $\exp(-Et)$ or $\langle x \rangle$

We wish to suggest an alternate approach which uses neither $\langle x \rangle$ nor $\exp(-Et)$. We first consider only the infinite square well potential and write two classical energy conservation equations using energies E_n and E_m which correspond to two adjacent high n, m quantum levels. Then:

$E_n = .5m (v + dv)^2 + V(x)$ and $E_m = .5m v^2 + V(x)$ $n=m+1$

Subtracting the two yields $E_n - E_m \approx m v dv$ ((8))

We call $v=dx/dt$ and $mdv = dp$ which we set equal to the quantum result: $dp = 2\pi \hbar/L$ ((9)).

Then: $(E_n - E_m) dt = dx \cdot 2\pi \hbar/L$. One may integrate over dx and dt to find:

$(E_n - E_m) T = 2\pi \hbar$ or $T = 2\pi \hbar / (E_n - E_m)$ ((10))

((10)) is the result from (1). Again, $E_n - E_m \approx dE/dn$ at n .

The above result for an infinite potential well also holds in special relativity i.e.

$E_n = \gamma m_0 c^2 (v+dv)^2 + m_0 c^2$ and $E_m = \gamma m_0 c^2 v^2 + m_0 c^2$

Subtracting and using $E_n = E_m + \Delta E$ yields: $(\gamma = 1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2})$

$\Delta p = \hbar \Delta k$ or: $\Delta p = \hbar \Delta k$ where $\Delta p = \hbar \Delta k = 2\pi \hbar / \lambda$
 again in quantum mechanics

Thus: $T = \hbar / (E_n - E_m) = \hbar / dE/dn$ at n ((11))

Thus, the infinite well potential approach holds also in special relativity.

Speculation for General Potentials in the Nonrelativistic Case

We try to see if the above approach may be extended to general potentials. In such a case, one cannot use a priori: $\Delta p = \hbar / \lambda$ because this only holds for a square well potential.

Using ((8)) i.e. $(E_n - E_m) \Delta t = \Delta x \Delta p$

Here Δp is the difference in $p(n)$ and $p(m)$, i.e. for different energy solutions.

One must integrate on the LHS, i.e. $\int dt = T$. Matters on the RHS side are more complicated

We note that $\Delta x \Delta p$ is reminiscent of the Heisenberg uncertainty principle, which involves an integral using wavefunctions $W(x)$. (2)

$\Delta x \Delta p = \hbar/2$ ((12))

If, for some reason, the following were to hold:

$(E_n - E_m) T = \hbar/2 C_1$ where $C_1 = \text{constant}$ ((13))

then one could find C_1 by considering examples such as the infinite well potential and oscillator and find that: $C_1 = 4\pi$. One may note that equality is taken in the Heisenberg uncertainty case because E_n and E_m are adjacent states. This approach is, however, very hand-wavy.

An alternative approach to dealing with $\Delta x \Delta p$ is the following. Given that this is a high energy limit, a particle essentially moves freely with a constant velocity in each little Δx region, with its velocity being different in the next Δx . In other words, it is like $V(x)$ is a different constant in each Δx region.

The key idea is that in the high energy limit there is essentially no tunneling and so the particle is almost in an infinite well system with L being the distance between the classical turning points.

In such a case, the system length L determines the Δp changes allowed. In general, $\exp(ipx)$ is calculated for free particles which range over the allowed x . Then one combines these to create a bound wavefunction: $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. Here, these p values must satisfy $p = \hbar k = 2\pi \hbar n / L$ where L is the distance between classical turning points. These then superpose to create a wavefunction which satisfies the time-independent Schrodinger equation.

Thus: $dp = \hbar \cdot 2\pi / L$ like in the infinite well potential case.

In such situation ((13)) becomes:

$$(E_n - E_m) dt = dx dp \rightarrow T = \hbar \cdot 2\pi / (E_n - E_m) \approx \hbar \cdot 2\pi / dE/dn \text{ at } n \quad ((15))$$

Thus, the same equation holds as in the infinite well potential case and may be applied to situations with potentials, such as the harmonic oscillator as already shown.

Conclusion

In conclusion, revival arguments in the literature (1) are used to calculate the longest period for $\langle x \rangle$. These calculations are based on using $\exp(-iEt)$ and lead to a period for $\langle x \rangle$ of $T = \hbar \cdot 2\pi / (E_n - E_m) \approx \hbar \cdot 2\pi / dE/dn$ at n .

Here we argue that one may obtain this result without using notions of $\langle x \rangle$ or $\exp(-iEt)$. Instead, we consider classical conservation of energy equations for E_n , E_m with E_n and E_m being quantum adjacent energies for the high energy level case. The two equations are: $E_n = .5m(v+dv)(v+dv) + V(x)$ and $E_m = .5mvv + V(x)$. Subtracting yields: $(E_n - E_m) = v m dv$ (nonrelativistically). We solve this for the infinite well potential using $dp = m dv = \hbar \cdot 2\pi / L$ and obtain the classical period. (We show that for the square well potential, the results also hold in the special relativistic case.)

Next, we consider the more general case of a potential. In the high energy limit, we suggest that a particle is confined within classical turning points and so it is as if the particle is in an infinite well potential. In other words, the $\exp(ipx)$ basis functions must now satisfy infinite well boundary conditions and allowed p values are $\hbar \cdot 2\pi n / L$ where $n=1,2,3,\dots$

Thus, dp is once again $\hbar \cdot 2\pi / L$. In each dx , the particle is like a free particle with a certain p , so we suggest that dp is $\hbar \cdot 2\pi / L$ in each dx . As a result, $(E_n - E_m) \int dt = \hbar \cdot 2\pi / L \int dx$ and one obtains the result of (1), namely that;

$$T = \hbar \cdot 2\pi / (E_n - E_m) \approx \hbar \cdot 2\pi / dE/dn \text{ at } n.$$

References

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